

CARBON FIBER CLOTH REINFORCED Al COMPOSITES BY PRESSURE-REGULATED INFILTRATION

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber cloth reinforced metal matrix composites are analyzed for their liquid infiltration. Three kinds of spaces, which are layer space between two pieces of cloth, bundle space between bundles in a same piece and fiber space between fibers in one fiber bundle, are obeyed different laws and the resistances in different spaces are calculated and compared, in the adiabatic process. The flow resistance in the layer space is less than 0.15MPa/CM when V_f is less than 0.35. The flow resistance in the bundle space is also rather lower (less than 0.25MPa/CM) and does not change very much with the change of V_f . The resistance in the fiber space of both flow and capillary is rather high and increase of wettability is a effective method for melt infiltration in the spaces.

Keywords: Metal Matrix Composite, Infiltration and Carbon fiber Cloth.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal-matrix composites (MMCs) have attractive properties, but the high cost of those materials should be decreased of the techniques available for MMC fabrication. The melt infiltration process is the most highly developed, being in significant commercial use and offering a combination of technical versatility, attractive process economics, and good

microstructural control.

The technique is based on the injection of a liquid melt into the space within an assemble of ceramic fibers. Some previous publications have been presented for analyzing different feature of the infiltration process, including coverage of the microsegregation characteristics, the interfacial structure, the critical pressure for infiltrating a uniform preform, and thermal parameters^[1~3].

The properties of fibers will be devepoled in their anxial direction, therefore, fibers in composites is generally in directional arrangement. Carbon fiber cloth is a kind of weaves with two dimensions and is a common reinforcement in the resin matrix composites. Therefore, carbon fiber cloth pile as the reinforcement of MMCs is a practical application and the infiltration of the cloth pile is very interesting. The purpose of the present paper is to present a analysis for the infiltration and flow of molten metal in carbon fiber cloth pile.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The pressure-regulated infiltration equipment is schematically shown in Figure 1. The melt is preheated before being infiltrated into a carbon fiber cloth piled in the die. The die is preheated to a predetermined temperature. The fiber cloth has been coated with SiC and SiC + Si coatings by chemical vapour deposition. The matrix used in this research is Al-7%Si-0.35%Mg (356) alloy. The upper chamber is vacuumized at first and then compressed air is leded into the lower chamber and acted on the molten metal and the increasing speed of air pressure is adjusted by the controller. The molten metal is infiltrated into fiber preform through a pipe connected the two chambers. The infiltrated metal solidificates under the maximum pressure. The composites are characterized to study the effect of infiltration.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of infiltration apparatus.

3. PROCESS ANALYSIS OF INFILTRATION

The fiber array in a carbon fiber cloth is represented in Figure 2(a). As a crude approximation, all fiber bundles, including warp and weft bundles, are arrayed uniformly in same interval. The interval of two fiber bundles is a and the width of a bundle weaved in cloth is d . Their values are depended on the kind of carbon fiber cloth.

A schematic illustration of carbon fiber cloth pile is given in figure 2(b). The distance between two neighbouring layers is h , which is a function of fiber volume fraction (V_f). The thickness of a layer is c . There are two ways of melt infiltration in the pile as shown in the Figure 2(b). Melt flows in the direction of along the (a), laminar flow in the spaces between fiber laminate cloth, and (b), through mesh flow in the direction

Figure 2. Illustrations of (a) fiber array in a piece of fiber cloth and (b) fiber cloth pile and melt infiltration.

of perpendicular to the cloth laminae. These two infiltrations and flows obey different laws.

Many factors influence the flow and infiltration of melt metal in fiber preforms. Of them thermal heat factors and fluid mechanics factors are of most importance. Heat factors influence the viscosity and solidification process of melt and some researchers have studied some simple cases. Owing to very shord time of flow the process can be treated as an adiabatic process.

The spaces in the fiber cloth pile are the most important parameter to calculate resistance in fluid mechanics in the infiltration process. There are three kinds of spaces in the pile, layer space, bundle space and fiber space. Layer space is a submillimeter space and its value decrease with the increase of V_f . It is two dimensional lamina. The bundle space has submillimeter size and the fiber spase has a submicron size.

As an approximation, the flow in the two dimensional laminae can be treated on the basis of the flow in the two parallel plates, and the pressure drop of the flow can be calculated from following equation^[4];

$$\frac{\Delta P}{L} = \frac{3\mu V}{\left(\frac{h}{2}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where ΔP is pressure drop. L is the length of the flow route, μ is the dynamic viscosity of molten metal, V is the velocity of the flow and h is the distance of close two layers.

The pressure drop of the flow through mesh can be calculate by the drag theory but by Darcy law since the fiber fraction volume is less than that in general porous medium. The drag theory assumes that the pressure drop to overcome viscous drag is linear addition of every single fibers. During the begining period the fiber bundle can be traeted as a thick fiber, because melt only enters large spaces. Therefore, the pressure drop of the flow can be calculated from following equation^[5];

$$\frac{\Delta P}{L} = \frac{4\pi N\mu V}{2 - \ln Re} \quad (2)$$

Where N is the number of fiber bundles per unit volume and Re is Reynolds number of melt.

When melt flow in the fiber spaces with submicron size, both viscous and capillary resistance are larger. The viscous resistance will become less, if melt entry the space with rather less velocity. This entry is maily opposed by the necessity of generating meniscus curvature at the infiltration front. The pressure difference is given by the Kelvin equation

$$P_i = \sum_j \sigma / r_j \quad (3)$$

where r_j are the principal radii of curvature and σ is interfacial force at the melt-atmosphere interface. Any development of wettability of fiber by melt would reduced curvature. In the case of uniform arrangement, the minimum predicted value can be obtained from the equation. On the other hand, non-uniform arrangement of fiber in a bundle would probably require higher melt curvature for penetration than the idea uniform arrangement. For example, suppose there is a two dimensional space with wedge, the pres-

sure difference is given by following equation^[6]

$$P = \sigma_L \sin\left(\theta - \alpha - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) / L \sin\alpha \quad (4)$$

where θ is the contact angle at the melt-atmosphere-fiber, α is the wedge angle and L is the length of wedge. It is worth noting that in the non-wetting systems, the pressure difference can become infinity.

It is obviously of interest to compare the pressures of the three different spaces in the carbon fiber cloth pile for the melt flow and infiltration, as is done in figure 3. In general the conclusion is that the spaces have very different resistances.

Figure 3. Predicted variation with fiber volume fraction of the pressure drop in different spaces.

4. COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURE

The pressure of molten metal is a main parameter in the infiltration of a carbon fiber cloth pile. Typical transverse section of a composite fabricated under lower infiltration pressure is shown in Figure 4(a). The infiltration of molten metal is rather perfectly in the layer space and in the bundle spaces, but the infiltration is failure in the fiber spaces. The appearance can hardly be improved by increasing finite pressure of infiltration, as

Figure 4. Optical micrographs of sections from composites infiltrated (a) at 0.1 MPa (b) at 1.5 MPa (c) at 800°C preheated temperature of fibers and (d) with wettable fiber coating.

shown in Figure 4(b). In fact, the result can be predicted from the theory analysis. In the analysis a same velocity of flow was suggested for keeping the process adiabatic. The resistance in fiber spaces can be decreased by decreasing the velocity of flow in the spaces only if the solidification are eliminated. In terms of theory that can be achieved by increasing the prehead of temperature of fibers, but the infiltration of the fiber spaces cannot be improved by increasing the preheat temperature of fibers, as shown in Figure 4(c). The capillary resistance will become very significant in fiber space in micrometer size, therefore, capillary resistance is the main obstruction of infiltration and high preheat temperature cannot solve the problem. The infiltration effect becomes better with the pressure increasing, but even if the pressure is very high, some microvoids can be found in composites. The predicted values of infiltration pressure from eq. 2 is a minimum value for uniform distribution of fiber in a bundle. In fact, the fiber spaces are far not uniform. Considering a simple two-dimensional wedge of half angle α at its base in bundles, and the contact angle is θ , the pressure that must be supplied to move reversibly the

liquid metal a little further into the wedge is clear that the pressure will become infinite with the being very small. On the other hand, microwedges will be infiltrated spontaneously in a wetting system as shown in Figure 4(d).

5. Conclusion

The liquid infiltration for fiber cloth reinforced MMC has been analyzed. The analysis is oriented toward an approximately a carbon fiber cloth pile with the volume fraction of fibers in the range 10 pct to 50 pct. The three spaces in fiber cloth pile: layer space, bundle space and fiber space obey different laws in the liquid infiltration process. The pressure drop in the layer spaces and bundle spaces of a melt flow is rather lower, so that the infiltration or flow in these spaces is easy. The drag resistance and capillary resistance both are very high in the fiber space, so that the entry and infiltration of melt in the spaces is difficult by increasing infiltration pressure, but it is effective method by improving the wetting properties between fibers and melt.

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